

“Martin Eden” as a Nietzschean Hero: Idealism, Alienation, and Disillusionment

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***Abstract.** The article examines life which is guided by Nietzschean theory ultimately ends in failure. The protagonist’s intellectual journey ends tragically in “Martin Eden”. His striving for greatness was initially driven by his pure love for his beloved. Entering the world of knowledge, he begins to think deeply and philosophically. As Martin’s worldview broadens, he realizes that representatives of the bourgeois class look down on ordinary people and act unjustly toward them.*

***Keywords:** Nietzschean tragedy, society, knowledge, philosophy of life, complex character, real events, failure.*

INTRODUCTION.

Jack London portrays Martin Eden as a kind and compassionate person. The care shown to him by others awakens kindness in his heart. Martin buys shoes, toys, and sweets for his landlady Maria and her children, demonstrating his generosity. He helps his sisters and brothers-in-law and even buys a farm for Maria, showing that he has risen to the level of a noble and complex character.

As a realist writer, Martin decides to write engaging works based on real characters and events. Having developed into a complex intellectual figure, he gains the ability to analyze scientific theories critically. For this reason, the society in which he lives does not accept his views. As a result, he is regarded as an “enemy of society.” Even Ruth sends him a letter expressing regret that they belong to different social classes and that she opposed her parents’ wishes. Martin grows disillusioned with life, feeling like a sailor swimming against the current, as if his hopes and dreams have faded.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION.

In her article “Martin Eden: the Nietzschean Tragedy,” Anna Huhanantti argues that a life guided by Nietzschean theory ultimately ends in failure. Martin Eden’s intellectual journey ends tragically. His striving for greatness was initially driven by his pure love for his beloved. Entering the world of knowledge, he begins to think deeply and philosophically.

As Martin’s worldview broadens, he realizes that representatives of the bourgeois class look down on ordinary people and act unjustly toward them. Hatred for this class arises in his heart. Once he had admired those with university diplomas and bank accounts, but his philosophy of life changes completely. Due to society’s unjust treatment, he loses his beloved and begins to lose hope in life. The protagonist, who had always strived for success, stops writing literary works. He feels isolated and alone, cut off from society. Martin Eden sees himself as a person without purpose or dreams, lost on his path, as if he has fallen into a dark void.

But within two years, Martin’s manuscripts – previously firmly rejected – began to be accepted by magazines one after another. Even when his work “*The Disgraced Sun*” was published, it did not bring joy to his heart. He received large sums of money for the books he had written. However, Martin had already lost interest in money. He gave the money he earned to his relatives. The protagonist’s works were distributed in forty thousand copies across the United States.

Within a short period, Martin’s writings spread throughout the entire country and captured the hearts of readers. He shone on the horizon of literature like a star and became a wealthy and famous man.

CONCLUSION.

After Martin Eden became recognized as a famous writer, he was constantly invited to banquets. Even his brother-in-law Bernard Higginbotham, who had once completely

disregarded him, began inviting him as a guest. Martin was astonished by his brother-in-law's sudden kindness, because when he had been starving and exhausting himself writing literary works, no one had invited him to dinner.

When he had withdrawn from society, living in isolation, going hungry for weeks and immersing himself in his creative work, people had looked down on Martin Eden. Now that he had enough money to feed a hundred thousand people, those around him began to value him. The protagonist condemned the injustice of life. Representatives of the bourgeoisie had accused him of being “lazy” and a “vagabond.” Once his manuscripts were published in newspapers and magazines and he became known to the public, society's attitude toward him changed completely. He even became an honored guest in the Morse household. Now the members of the Morse family considered Martin a suitable suitor for Ruth.

Representatives of bourgeois society began to treat Martin as if he were a noble and distinguished man of high status because of the works he had written, his fame, and the hundred thousand dollars in his bank account. Previously, the girl he loved, Ruth, had demanded that Martin find a job because his “Love Sonnets” brought in no income.

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